

Revitalising Macau Old Protestant Cemetery with Engaging Interactive Design for Cultural Preservation

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Figure 1: Drawing Map of Macau Old Protestant Cemetery. Image by Root 我城社區規劃合作社, 2017

Abstract

The study aims to contribute to current efforts to conserve Macau's Cultural Heritage (Macau Old Protestant Cemetery) via digital methods, improve user experiences, and foster creative interactions with Macau's cultural sites by investigating the usage of mobile applications and immersive technologies such as augmented reality (AR) and visual graphics for mobile applications.

Keywords

Mobile Application Design, Augmented Reality, Visual Graphics, Cultural Preservation, Macau Old Protestant Cemetery

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

“The Historic Centre of Macau” was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List in 2005, featuring over 20 monuments and 30 distinct sights; it showcases the city's rich blend of Chinese and Portuguese cultural influences. To enhance accessibility and preservation, Macau's government has developed mobile apps (<https://www.wh.mo/whmacau/>) and virtual reality tours (<https://vr.icm.gov.mo/>) of these heritage sites since 2005 and 2021 [1]. Recognizing the widespread adoption and convenience of mobile applications, which offer personalized and interactive experiences, there is an opportunity to further enhance the exploration of Macau's cultural heritage through a dedicated mobile app, potentially incorporating advanced reality technologies like AR and VR.

1.2 Purpose and Motivation

The book “Cemeteries in Macau” records a lot of different types of cemeteries in the Macau Peninsula, Taipa, and Coloane. Macau Old Protestant Cemetery is a significant historical site on the UNESCO World Heritage List. It holds the remains of pivotal figures like Dr Robert Morrison (the first Protestant missionary), George Chinnery (a famous English printer), and Anders Ljungstedt (a Swedish merchant and historian), making it a crucial window into the development of Protestantism and early foreign relations in Macau [2].

Despite its historical importance, exploring and promoting the site further is necessary, particularly considering evolving travel trends. The increasing popularity of self-guided exploration and virtual experiences, especially post-pandemic, suggests a growing demand for deeper, more personalized cultural engagement. Macau is a city with a rich cultural legacy, ideal for self-exploration. A drawing map (Figure 1) of the old protestant cemetery was created by the Root art organization, and the authors are motivated by the desire to provide a more comprehensive and accessible understanding of Macau Old Protestant Cemetery, catering to the modern traveler's desire for unique and enriching cultural experiences.

1.3 Research Objectives

Use interactive experiences to raise awareness and understanding of the historic value of Macau Old Protestant Cemetery. Use modern technology, particularly mobile applications, to offer an immersive platform for visitors to interact with and understand the cemetery's history. Spread information about the cemetery's establishment and historical significance to a larger audience.

1.4 Research Question

How might interactive mobile applications with (AR experiences) improve awareness and enjoyment of Macau’s cultural legacy, particularly emphasizing Macau’s Old Protestant Cemetery?

2 Literature review

2.1 Interactive Technologies for Cultural Heritage

Interactive Technologies have been used in mobile applications for cultural heritages; users can interact with digital objects and environments to create a sense of presence and engagement [3.]. Marker-based AR is widely used with visual cues like QR codes to identify the digital information on screens [4.], and 360-degree virtual tours use panoramic images from some fixed points to present the space [5.]. Introducing technologies such as multimedia guides makes the museum experience more engaging for visitors [6.]. The authors attempt to offer a mobile application as the platform for an AR and virtual tour experience and spread the historical information to audiences.

2.2 Visual Graphics & Storytelling

Visual storytelling is vital in engaging audiences and keeping their attention longer. Many museums and exhibitions use interactive digital storytelling to enhance the visiting experience [7.]. AR brings the story elements into the real world, while VR places users directly into story environments [8.]. The authors plan to spread the stories of the burials at the cemetery in AR for users to learn about the historical value of the cemetery and enhance their interaction with the heritage site.

2.3 Cultural Preservation and Mobile Application

In 2003, UNESCO adopted a Charter on preserving digital heritage. The Charter mentioned, “The purpose of preserving the digital heritage is to ensure that it remains accessible to the public.” [9.] Since then, art galleries and museums have begun to transfer their art into digital copies and store them. The loss of cultures seems undeniable, but interconnectivity and digital technologies may play a vital role in protecting cultural diversity. Tourists use mobile applications for information about cultural sites and landmarks, historical and ethnographic museums, and various interesting events. The mobile applications developed for tourism aim to enhance the user experience by integrating multiple technologies, especially for places and heritage sites with limited access, great historical value, and diverse information to share [10.].

2.4 History of Macau and Cemeteries in Macau

Macau is a historical and cultural city on a land of only 29 square kilometers. “The Historic Center of Macau” represents the architectural legacies of the city’s cultural heritage. Many cities worldwide are famous for their relatively single cultural uniqueness, but the intersection and integration of multiple cultures characterize Macau. Since its opening in the mid-16th century, Macau has been an essential bridge between the East and the West, and the religions represented in the cemeteries are likewise highly different. There

Figure 2: Graphical Map of Cemeteries in Macau. Image by Lau, 2024

are Buddhism, Catholicism, Christianity, Islam, and Zoroastrianism. Because Macau’s population is primarily Chinese and Portuguese, most inhabitants practice Buddhism and Catholicism. The Macau Old Protestant Cemetery was built in 1821. Before the cemetery was built, the Catholic Church in Macau was in a privileged position and did not allow Protestants to be buried within the city walls. At the same time, the Chinese people also did not allow foreigners to be buried in the customs area. Therefore, merchants from the United Kingdom, the United States, and Scandinavian countries had to be buried secretly between the city walls and the customs area [11.]. The total number of cemeteries in Macau is listed below and illustrated (Figure 2): Cemeteries in Peninsula of Macao: 6, Cemeteries in Taipa Island: 5, Cemeteries in Coloane Island: 6, Total: 17.

3 Methodology

The study methodology includes case studies of mobile apps and VR tour websites in Macau. Also, the authors surveyed the background knowledge of Macau cemeteries and users’ preferences. The project will use a design thinking approach to develop a mobile application prototype with interactive technologies like Augmented Reality (AR) and a 360 virtual tour on the website. Usability testing was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the prototype in achieving the research objectives.

3.1 Case Studies

WH Macau (Figure 3)

- WH Macau is a mobile app created by Macau’s cultural heritage.
- It provides information about Macau’s heritage sites.

It offers heritage routes, news, activities, and photo galleries.

Figure 3: Mobile Application WH Macau. Image from the App Store, 2024

Figure 4: Virtual tour scene for Ruins of St. Paul virtual tour. Authors Instituto Cultural, 2014

The Instituto Cultural launched the “Online Virtual Tours (VR) Website,” which created the tours of the heritage sites in 4 languages with floor plans, and users can access different site areas with 360-degree photos and listen to the audio guiding of the regions (Figure 4).

In summary, the case studies above have shown the availability of applying digital methods to Macau’s heritage, but the authors considered the complexity of the user experience and the attractiveness of the heritage. A more user-friendly interface and fun interaction with the sites are needed as a new try for the prototype.

3.2 Design of the Prototype

The prototype is a mobile application for Macau Old Protestant Cemetery, including interactive technology functionalities such as an AR experience and 360 virtual tours. The AR experience is about four famous figures from the cemetery. To interact with the AR experience, a storytelling visual timeline board is provided with QR codes; the 360 virtual tour is with 16 pictures taken from different site locations, and the tour was created in an online platform that can be linked to the mobile application.

3.2.1 Timeline Design. To sort out all the different materials and select the valuable contents for the leaflet, the authors concentrate the historical information into two parts: Famous Figures and Historical Events as a visual timeline (Figure 5).

3.2.2 AR Experience Creation. As it has been highlighted that the historical figures are the main features of Macau Old Protestant Cemetery, four figures with their significant contribution have been settled in the ideation of the AR experience using Adobe Aero (Figure 6).

([https://youtube.com/shorts/rrYoR43SwHY?feature\\$=\\$share](https://youtube.com/shorts/rrYoR43SwHY?feature$=$share),
[https://youtube.com/shorts/zYlzfmmw_CUQ?feature\\$=\\$share](https://youtube.com/shorts/zYlzfmmw_CUQ?feature$=$share),
[https://youtube.com/shorts/iGiDf2-JaQA?feature\\$=\\$share](https://youtube.com/shorts/iGiDf2-JaQA?feature$=$share),
[https://youtube.com/shorts/xquTT1UsqOg?feature\\$=\\$share](https://youtube.com/shorts/xquTT1UsqOg?feature$=$share)).

3.2.3 360°Experience Tour. A virtual tour of Macau Old Protestant Cemetery is created due to the perfect preservation of the site; users can interact with the space on a virtual tour online platform Kuula (Figure 7). ([https://kuula.co/share/collection/7KPJd?logo\\$=\\$1&info\\$=\\$1&fs\\$=\\$1&vr\\$=\\$0&sd\\$=\\$1&thumbs\\$=\\$1](https://kuula.co/share/collection/7KPJd?logo$=$1&info$=$1&fs$=$1&vr$=$0&sd$=$1&thumbs$=$1)).

3.2.4 Mobile Application Prototype. The mobile application prototype created by Adobe XD contains all the functionalities; the user can scan the QR code on the visual timeline board to access the AR experience, and the 360-degree tour is linked directly to the website (Figure 8). ([https://xd.adobe.com/view/a42e34c7-9ea4-400b-bc9a-52ad71a6f53d-f17d/?mv\\$=\\$other&mv2\\$=\\$ahome&promoid\\$=\\$XKMMH7MW&xProduct\\$=\\$&xProductLocation\\$=\\$](https://xd.adobe.com/view/a42e34c7-9ea4-400b-bc9a-52ad71a6f53d-f17d/?mv$=$other&mv2$=$ahome&promoid$=$XKMMH7MW&xProduct$=$&xProductLocation$=$)).

3.3 Usability Testing

In the usability testing of the prototype, the authors gathered 20 participants who were not familiar with Macau Protestant Cemetery, aged from 25 to 50, and skilled with mobile technologies. Question 1 is about how they feel about the product in terms of usability, quality, instructiveness, and durability; Question 2 asks how much fun and excitement they have with the interactive event; Question 5 is to see how likely they will recommend the prototype to their friends and colleagues. The responses show that most of the participants expressed appreciation for the innovation and instruction of the prototype and think that the product features are very educational and provide a new perspective on learning Macau’s history,

Figure 5: The layout design for the visual timeline. Image by Lau, 2024

Figure 6: AR Experience Creation and Outcome. Image by Lau, 2024

especially for the Macau Old Protestant Cemetery. Meanwhile, some of them may be concerned about the sustainability of the app as it just focuses on the cemetery.

4 Conclusion

This study successfully explored integrating AR technology into a mobile application to enhance cultural preservation at Macau Old Protestant Cemetery. Through literature review, historical research, case studies, and usability testing, the authors demonstrated the potential of interactive technology to engage users with unfamiliar heritage sites in Macau. However, the authors acknowledge limitations. Firstly, the methodology must be tailored to the unique

characteristics of each heritage site. Secondly, technological constraints necessitated multiple tools, highlighting the need for a fully integrated mobile application. Furthermore, we strategically limited the information presented to avoid overwhelming users.

The paper serves as a stepping stone towards a future where technology effectively bridges the gap between historical preservation and public engagement in Macau, and the authors encourage further research into the application of interactive experiences for cultural preservation.

Figure 7: 360°Experience Tours Shots. Image by Lau, 2024

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Figure 8: Mobile Application UI/UX Design. Image by Lau, 2024

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